

Migration of Syrian Refugees to Turkey and the Impact of Bashar al-Assad's Departure on Return Decisions

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Abstract

This study examines the reasons behind the migration of Syrian refugees who sought asylum in Turkey following the outbreak of the civil war in 2011, their living experiences in Turkey, and their return intentions after the resignation of Bashar al-Assad as of December 8, 2024. Based on survey data, the analysis reveals that the majority of refugees prefer to remain in Turkey, with major obstacles to return being concerns over security and economic uncertainty. The radical structure of the new Syrian administration (HTS and its leader Ahmed al-Shara) acts as a deterrent for many refugees. During the integration process in Turkey, challenges such as language barriers, economic hardship, and social incompatibility are prominent. Turkey needs to develop policies that support integration and prepare the infrastructure for voluntary and safe return.

Keywords: Syrian refugees, Return, Assad's resignation, HTS (Hay'at Tahrir al-Sham), Turkey's migration policies, International support, Future of Syrians

Research Objective: The purpose of this paper is to examine the refugees who migrated to Turkey from Syria, where civil unrest began in 2011, and their decision to return after Assad's departure as of December 8, 2024. This study will also evaluate the factors related to the return process of asylum seekers.

Research Scope: The research covers Syrian asylum-seekers who migrated to Turkey after the beginning of the civil war in Syria in 2011. Moreover, the impact of Assad's departure and the political situation in Syria on the decision of asylum-seekers to stay in Turkey or return is analyzed through a mini survey.

Research Question:

- What factors influence Syrian refugees' decision to migrate to Turkey?
- How would Assad's departure affect refugees' decision to return to Syria?
- What is the impact of living conditions in Turkey on asylum seekers' decision to return?

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Survey Content and Measurement-Evaluation Method: In this study, a mini survey was conducted to understand Syrian refugees' life experiences in Turkey, the challenges they face and the impact of Assad's departure on their decision to return. The questionnaire was designed both to collect demographic information and to measure the respondents' views on their life in Turkey, their thoughts on returning to Syria, and the political situation.

Survey Content: The questionnaire consists of questions gathered under four main headings: Demographic Questions: Questions on Returning to Syria, Opinions on the Situation in Syria, Future Plans and General Opinions.

Assessment Method: The evaluation of the questionnaire was based on frequency analysis of participants' responses. The responses to the questions were collected using Likert-type scales (e.g. "Yes", "No", "Undecided") and then grouped into various categories. In this way, factors such as participants' plans to return to Syria, their level of satisfaction with living conditions in Turkey, and the impact of Assad's departure on their decision to return were analyzed.

The data were analyzed using statistical analysis software such as **SPSS** and the relationships between the demographic characteristics of the participants and their opinions were determined. In addition, for **qualitative data**, participants' explanations and written opinions were evaluated by thematic analysis.

Syrian Refugees Survey Results and Evaluation

Most of the Syrian asylum-seekers who participated in the survey are young adults between the ages of 26-35. Men are overrepresented in gender distribution. Their family structures are generally large and consist of 4-6 people on average. Most of the respondents live in Istanbul, one of the cities with the largest Syrian population in Turkey.

Decision to Stay in Turkey According to the survey results, most Syrian asylum-seekers prefer to stay in Turkey under current conditions. Language barrier and economic difficulties stand out among the biggest factors that make it difficult to live in Turkey. Issues such as finding a job, education and social cohesion pose significant obstacles for asylum-seekers. Nevertheless, advantages in Turkey, such as access to health and education services, are among the incentives for asylum-seekers to stay. Those who find some opportunities in the labor market find it more rational to stay in Turkey.

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Decision to Leave Turkey The rate of those who intend to return to Syria is relatively low and most refugees are undecided about returning. Among those who are considering return, the biggest motivation is the improvement of the security situation and the desire to be close to family. However, the current uncertainties and economic instability in Syria make this decision difficult. The results of the survey indicate that a change in the Assad regime may affect the decision to return for some people. However, negative views about the new administration in Syria (HTS) are predominant, which further weakens the idea of return.

The biggest barrier to return for asylum-seekers is security concerns. Unless there is a secure environment in Syria, many refugees do not intend to return. Economic uncertainty is also an important factor, with lack of job opportunities and low basic living standards delaying the decision to return. In addition, for some asylum-seekers, family ties and social assistance provided in Turkey are other factors complicating the decision to return.

Most Syrian refugees are undecided about staying in Turkey, with some considering the option of moving to another country. For those who are considering staying in Turkey, the greatest needs are economic support and security guarantees. The idea of going to other countries often seems more attractive for individuals seeking economic opportunities. However, uncertainty about return remains and a large-scale return movement seems unlikely at the moment.

According to the survey results, the majority of Syrian asylum-seekers prefer to stay in Turkey, but are uncertain about the future due to the economic and social difficulties they face here. Language barrier and limited job opportunities constitute an important obstacle in the integration process in Turkey. On the other hand, the health and education services provided by Turkey stand out as a positive factor for asylum-seekers.

The biggest obstacle to return to Syria is security and economic uncertainty. Asylum-seekers find it difficult to make a definite decision about staying in Turkey, they shape their future plans more according to economic and security factors. Developing policies that support the integration process of Syrian asylum-seekers who will stay in Turkey can improve their quality of life and facilitate their integration into society.

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In the long term, Turkey should make the necessary infrastructure preparations for the safe and sustainable return of Syrian refugees. In this process, economic incentives to support return, plans to create safe zones and international cooperation are crucial. A comprehensive strategy should be developed to ensure the voluntary and human rights compliant return of refugees.

Introduction

In March 2011, since the beginning of the civil unrest in Syria, an increasing number of Syrian Arab Republic (Syrian) nationals have arrived in Turkey seeking international protection. Turkey has provided and continues to provide them with "temporary protection". The rapid increase in human rights violations in Syria in 2012 and beyond has led to a dramatic increase in humanitarian needs. Since the beginning of the civil unrest, the Republic of Turkey, which has strong historical, cultural and neighborly ties with Syria, has followed an "open door" policy for Syrian citizens affected by the situation.³

In line with this policy, Syrian refugees have been one of the most debated issues in Turkey since 2011 and this problem has directly affected both domestic and foreign policy. Especially in the aftermath of the civil unrest in Syria, the flow of migration to Turkey has increased rapidly, which has been a fundamental factor shaping the state's national and international policies. Today, the refugee issue has a significant impact not only on state policies but also on the daily life of the people, cultural structure and social dynamics. Migrants, especially Syrian asylum seekers, are forcing changes in the business world, politics and social structure.

This has led to significant changes in areas such as social cohesion, labor market and public services. The asylum-seeker issue has become a multidimensional problem that the government, local governments and civil society organizations are trying to solve. The cultural diversity and social tensions created by migrants have led to divisions and political polarization among the population, resulting in social unrest.

In terms of its political dimensions, the refugee issue has become a major point of contention in domestic politics. The policies of the government and the opposition on this issue affect the

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political environment in Turkey and have also been a decisive factor in Turkey's foreign relations, especially with the European Union and other international actors.

As of December 8, 2024, Syrian President Bashar al-Assad's administration was seized by military operations, the 61-year BAAS era came to an end and Assad sought refuge in Russia. With the end of the Baathist regime, a new era began for Syria.

Syrian Refugees in the Light of Statistics

The 2011 uprising in Syria and the ensuing conflict have forced more than 13 million people to be displaced. This has caused great losses to Syria and the Syrian people. While 6 million Syrians were internally displaced, more than 7 million were forced to leave their country.

According to UN data (Table 1), since 2011, people from conflict-affected areas have fled to Lebanon, Jordan, Iraq, Egypt, Egypt, North Africa and European countries, particularly Turkey. According to UN data, as of October 2020, a total of 7.276 million Syrians have sought refuge in other countries in the region, more than 3.6 million of them in Turkey. Compared to neighboring countries, Europe and America have been more cautious about asylum seekers . It is known that more than half of the refugees hosted by Europe live in Germany. According to statistics, the US and North American countries approach this problem with more distance. Indeed, Canada and the US alone are hosting less than 100,000 Syrians in total. Of the 6.7 million Syrian refugees who have crossed into neighboring countries, 93.7% remain outside refugee camps and more than 60% of these people are severe poverty ⁴

Table 1

Number of Syrian Refugees by Country (October 2020)	
Turkey	3.635.410

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Lebanon	1.200.000
European countries	884.461
Jordan	657.000
Iraq	233.224
Egypt	120.154
Egypt North Africa	29.27

Turkey's Migration Policies and Asylum Seekers

Number and Distribution of Syrian Refugees in Turkey

The size of the Syrian population in Turkey: As of October 2020, according to United Nations data, there were 3,635,410 Syrian asylum-seekers in Turkey, while according to the data of the Migration Administration dated January 30, 2025, this number is 2,863,472 registered Syrians. The difference is mostly Syrians who have acquired Turkish citizenship, but also a small number of Syrians who have left Turkey. Therefore, the current number of registered asylum-seekers in Turkey does not fully reflect the total Syrian population. Moreover, as these figures include registered asylum-seekers, it is estimated that there is a large unregistered population.

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YILLARA GÖRE GEÇİCİ KORUMA KAPSAMINDAKİ SURİYELİLER

*30.01.2025 tarihi itibariyle

Distribution of asylum-seekers by provinces; Most of the migrants who seek asylum in Turkey reside in metropolitan cities such as Istanbul, Ankara and Izmir instead of shelter centers such as camps. Although the settlement rate of Syrian asylum-seekers varies by province, it is now possible to find Syrians in all provinces of Turkey. In many cities, the number of Syrian asylum-seekers has become equivalent to the local population, and in some areas has exceeded it. Istanbul hosts the highest number of Syrians, while Bayburt hosts the lowest number of refugees. Some metropolitan cities, notably Istanbul, are closed to the intake of Syrians, yet they harbor the largest Syrian population. According to January 30, 2025 data from the Migration Administration, the distribution of Syrians in Turkey according to the top 10 provinces in terms of population density is shown in the table below.

Table 2.

GEÇİCİ KORUMA KAPSAMINDA BULUNAN SURİYELİLERİN İLK 10 İLE GÖRE DAĞILIMI

*30.01.2025 tarihi itibarıyla

Legal Framework: Turkey's Asylum Seeker Policies; Turkey has accepted the vast majority of Syrian asylum seekers within the framework of its open door policy. The 2013 Law on Foreigners and International Protection granted Syrians temporary protection status and in this context, they were given Temporary Protection Identity Documents. This document does not grant Syrians the right to reside in Turkey, nor does it grant them citizenship. However, under temporary protection status, Syrians can benefit from health services, education, access to the labor market, social assistance and other services.

As of September 2019, the number of Syrians registered under temporary protection in Turkey is 3,663,863, which corresponds to approximately 4.47% of Turkey's population of 82 million. Of the Syrians under temporary protection, 45.80% are women and 54.20% are men. Another striking feature of this population is the high proportion of children. Children between the ages of 0-14 constitute 1,438,582 of the total number of Syrian refugees in Turkey. In addition, the number of young people between the ages of 15-24 is 828,186 and the number of individuals aged 60 and over is 116,147. As of August 1, 2019, 92,280 Syrians have been naturalized as citizens of the Republic of Turkey outside the temporary protection status. Of this number

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47,000 are adults and 45,280 are children. In the same period, 337,729 Syrians returned to their country. ⁵

It is not possible to reach a precise figure for unregistered asylum-seekers. However, there are various assessments that the number of unregistered Syrian asylum-seekers is quite high. Asylum-seekers who try to enter Turkey through unregistered means and are apprehended are referred to Removal Centers for deportation in accordance with the relevant legislation.

Social Perception and Attitudes towards Syrians; The prolonged stay of Syrian asylum-seekers in Turkey has led to significant changes affecting the social and cultural structure, especially in border provinces, and has caused various reactions among local people. It is thought that the irregular and unplanned distribution of the majority of Syrian asylum-seekers living outside the accommodation centers to the cities has led to serious deterioration in the quality of urban life. This situation has a profound impact on the social structure of Turkey. The differences between the socio-cultural structure that Syrians come from and the socio-cultural structure of Turkish society are quite evident. In particular, there have been significant changes in the structural characteristics of social institutions in areas where Syrians live in large numbers and these changes are expected to deepen in the future. Changes in the institutions that constitute the basic building blocks of society, especially the family structure, may have consequences that will affect the whole society.

In areas with high concentrations of Syrians, for example, there has been a decrease in the age of marriage (especially for women) and an increase in birth rates. Minister of Interior Süleyman Soylu stated on September 19, 2019 that the number of Syrian babies born in Turkey is approximately 450,000. The increasing birth rates of asylum-seekers and the prolongation of their stay in Turkey raise concerns that the demographic structure of the country may change in the future, and a perception of threat has emerged at the social level. These developments may have a negative impact on social peace and may lead to bigger problems in the coming years.

Another important social problem is the integration problems of Syrian asylum-seekers into Turkish society. The ghettoization of migrants in certain regions and neighborhoods, especially

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in cities, is an important barrier to integration. Ghettoization leads to the isolation of asylum-seekers and this situation negatively affects social cohesion processes. In addition, ghettoization of asylum-seekers may accelerate their marginalization and lead to deeper social problems.

Public Opinion on Syrian Asylum Seekers; Public opinion in Turkey has developed various perceptions about Syrian asylum seekers. Concerns related to security and crime pave the way for the spread of negative attitudes towards Syrians. Social problems such as crime cases, begging and prostitution involving asylum-seekers can lead to deterioration in the social fabric. Moreover, declining living standards among locals, especially in provinces with a high Syrian population, lead to tensions and mutual grievances. In some regions, anti-Syrian sentiment is on the rise due to the high Syrian population, leading to widespread social discontent. Between 2014 and 2017, especially in border areas, there were serious tensions between Syrian asylum-seekers and the local population, leading to demonstrations and protests. Various factors such as accidents involving vehicles with Syrian license plates, criminal incidents, theft and commercial problems have triggered these tensions.

The difficulties experienced by the society in the adaptation of asylum-seekers to the settled life create obstacles to their effective participation in the economy and social life. The fact that Syrian asylum-seekers live collectively in certain areas (ghettoization) causes negative perceptions among Turkish people, while the formation of illegal groups and the emergence of illegal sectors threaten social peace. Moreover, asylum-seekers who come to Turkey for shelter and exhaust their savings have difficulties in meeting their basic needs and this situation brings public order problems to the agenda. Asylum-seekers who cannot pay their rents and have difficulties in finding food cannot find safe places to live and therefore they may live on the streets or in parks.

Relations between Local People and Asylum Seekers; The presence of Syrian asylum-seekers in Turkey has brought along various challenges in relations with local people. In provinces where asylum-seekers have settled intensively, the attitude of the public towards asylum-seekers has changed over time. In particular, the increase in crime rates and the proliferation of social problems such as begging and prostitution have had a negative impact on the local population's perception of asylum-seekers. Between 2014 and 2017, tensions between

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asylum-seekers and locals led to significant social conflicts, with a large proportion of the public expressing serious discomfort with the presence of asylum-seekers.

The economic hardship experienced by asylum-seekers has exacerbated security problems in urban areas. This may lead to more aggressive attitudes of local people towards asylum-seekers, especially in winter months when economic needs increase. The social disharmony of asylum-seekers further complicates their relations with the local population and this process threatens social peace.

The Future of Syrian Asylum Seekers; A frequently emphasized point during the admission of Syrian asylum seekers to Turkey is that they have the status of "guests" and in this sense they have to adapt. However, the attitudes of the local population seem to be more welcoming towards Syrians who are close to their own ethnic and religious identities, while tending to exclude other Syrians. While Arabs are more positive towards Arabs, Kurds towards Kurds, and Turks towards Turkmens, other ethnic groups are marginalized.

The integration problems faced by asylum-seekers are largely due to legislative deficiencies. These shortcomings lead to difficulties in Syrians' access to basic human rights, educational opportunities and economic resources. As a result, this situation leads to tensions and conflicts between both Syrian asylum-seekers and Turkish citizens. In some cases, Syrians who are excluded from social and economic life turn to crime and harm the social order through phenomena such as theft and violence. As a result, there are allegations that Syrian asylum-seekers turn to mafia-type organizations in order to protect themselves.

In an environment where anti-refugee and anti-migrant sentiment is widespread in society, the efforts of minority groups to integrate may be less likely to be successful. Similarly, it can be assumed that the integration policies of the state and civil society organizations will not be effective with these groups. Therefore, openness to change on both sides is a fundamental condition for the integration process to be successful.

As of today, the social exclusion of Syrians is an important problem. The exclusion and discontent against Syrians is based on socio-economic and cultural factors. Among the justifications for this exclusion are factors such as the fact that Syrians take the labor force of Turkish citizens, that they have a negative impact on the labor market, and that housing rents

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have increased. In particular, the increase in housing rents is not only limited to the rise in rents, but can also be associated with increases in food prices. Such economic problems are more palpable in daily life and more vital than social or cultural problems, thus creating a great deal of discomfort among the local population. It is crucial to develop and implement the necessary policies for Syrian refugees to live in harmony with the host society.

It is thought that a single step such as granting citizenship will not be sufficient to find solutions to the problems of integration and exclusion of Syrians. According to the public opinion survey conducted by President Erdoğan in his study titled "Syrians in Turkey: Social Acceptance and Cohesion", the issue of citizenship emerges as the most debated and problematic issue. This study clearly shows that the cultural distance between Turkish society and Syrians is quite large and that the negative attitude towards citizenship is widespread. Turkish citizens question the impact of Syrians as guests on jobs, property and other social opportunities. Citizenship for Syrians means that they are permanent in Turkey. With the prolonged stay of asylum-seekers and the impact of media coverage, negative changes in public perception are observed. The fact that Syrians are exempt from taxes and obligations causes an additional reaction among the public. Moreover, the fact that Syrian asylum-seekers are admitted to universities without exams, benefit from health services free of charge, and receive advantageous scholarships and social aids compared to Turkish citizens causes public reaction.

Impact of Syrian Asylum Seekers on the Turkish Economy; The impact of the large migrant population coming to Turkey on the economy is an important parameter. This large migrant population has brought a serious burden to the country's economy and it is stated that this burden has negative effects on welfare and poverty levels in Turkey. The state of the Republic of Turkey has borne a huge economic burden in areas such as the accommodation of asylum seekers, their integration process, education, employment and health services. In August 2019, according to the President's statements, expenditures in this area reached approximately 40 billion dollars.

In addition, the unregistered employment of asylum-seekers and their work as cheap labor has been an important factor leading to the problem of unemployment for citizens in Turkey. In this context, the employment of Syrian asylum seekers emerges as an important humanitarian problem. Syrian asylum-seekers living outside camps are employed in heavy labor with low wages, without insurance, job security and vocational training. This situation not only increases

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the unemployment rates of the local labor force , but also creates major problems in terms of humanitarian dimensions in the employment areas of asylum seekers.

Despite the huge budget Turkey has spent on Syrian refugees, the volume of trade between the two countries has remained far below pre-war levels. In other words, the high volume of trade with Syria has largely disappeared due to Turkey's stance on the war. The expenditures for Syrian refugees on the one hand, and the stagnation of trade on the other, have significantly affected Turkey economically.

In contrast to Turkey's expenditures on Syrian asylum-seekers, the financial assistance it receives from international organizations remains quite low. Although the European Union stated that it would provide €3 billion by the end of 2017 and €3 billion by the end of 2018, to date, only €3 billion has been allocated in two equal tranches in two periods covering 2016-2017 and 2018-2019. Of the €6 billion in operational funding provided by the European Union for 80 projects, €2.22 billion has been disbursed and €3.45 billion has been contracted (EU Commission Press Conference, May 17, 2019, Brussels). In addition, it is stated that the funds transferred to Turkey through the United Nations to be used for the services of Syrian refugees is around 600 million dollars.

The majority of Syrians initially welcomed this change with great joy and thousands of Syrian refugees in Turkey and other countries expressed this joy by returning home to Syria. However, this was a very limited number of returns. The United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) estimates that 115,000 Syrians have returned to Syria since December 8. In Turkey, according to a December 30 statement by the Ministry of Interior , 35,114 Syrians have voluntarily returned since December 8.⁶

One of the most important reasons for the limited number of migrants is that some Syrians are wary of the new authorities. This is because the new administration is headed by Abu Mohammed al-Julani, the radical jihadist leader of Hayat Tahrir al-Sham (HTS). Joulani's harsh views on social life do not resonate with the majority of Syrians. Abu Mohammed al-Julani, Syria's opposition leader and military commander, is President of Syria as of January 20, 2025. Joulani has abandoned his pseudonym and now uses his real name, Ahmed al-Shera. Moreover,

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although a new era has begun in Syria, many areas such as economic recovery, social cohesion and stabilization are at a disadvantage. Although the overthrow of the Assad regime led to a major change in Syria's political and social landscape, the change in the humanitarian crisis in the country has not been as rapid. In Syria, which was already in a serious humanitarian crisis, the fall of the Assad regime has created many challenges that need to be overcome. The long-standing political and economic instability in the country, inadequate infrastructure in the provision of basic services such as electricity, water and fuel, difficulties in accessing basic foodstuffs and high inflation, large-scale destruction of hospitals, schools, public buildings and civilian settlements, and psycho-social traumas caused by the 13-year civil war are vital for the future of Syria. While the fact that the UN and many international humanitarian organizations have rapidly started humanitarian aid and recovery activities after the fall of the regime is promising for the future of Syria, the magnitude of the funds and resources needed demonstrates the importance of the support of the international community for the reconstruction of Syria. The end of the 61-year-old Baathist regime has not eliminated the deep humanitarian crisis in Syria. Indeed, 13 years of civil war and conflict have led to the destruction of existing infrastructure networks, displaced millions of people and left large parts of the country's population in need of urgent humanitarian assistance. The humanitarian situation in Syria has become one of the worst humanitarian crises in the world, with millions of people struggling to access even basic needs such as food, water, health and education. Moreover, security concerns in Syria persist. Although the fall of the regime and the withdrawal of Russian and Iranian forces have ended the conflict in many areas, the situation on the ground in Syria is still highly volatile.⁷ In this respect, the international community's guidance towards Syria and the constructive policies of the interim government will be effective in Syria's future trajectory.

Conclusion e Evaluation

First of all, plans for the repatriation of asylum-seekers should be prepared on a rational basis, free from ideological prejudices. In this framework, as a first step, it is necessary to improve relations with the Syrian regime and find joint solutions to the problem. Because as long as the instability in Syria continues, it will not be possible to solve the migration problem. In other words, in order to prevent the ongoing migration from Syria to Turkey and to repatriate Syrians

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in Turkey, the civil war and political governance problem in Syria must first be solved. A collective will must be established at the international level to solve this problem. For this, international organizations, neighboring countries and world powers, especially international organizations, need to come together and develop joint plans. International organizations such as the United Nations and the European Union should be given active roles and some of the refugees should be resettled in countries other than Turkey. Otherwise, it is not possible for Turkey to cope with this problem both financially and socially.

In order to solve the refugee problem effectively, Turkey needs to reassess how long it can accommodate these refugees and to what extent it can mobilize international public opinion. Even if the country's material potential is sufficient in this context, the sociological, socio-psychological and domestic political relevance of this issue should be reviewed. At this point, the fact that anti-refugee sentiment has the potential to turn into a social outrage should be recognized. If anti-refugee/anti-asylum-seeker sentiment turns into a social outrage, the extent and target group of this outrage may be unpredictable and it will be very difficult to stop it. Therefore, this process should be kept on a rational basis and managed through democratic methods. The refugee problem and process should be handled in a way that is free from radicalism and provocation, in line with reasonable discourses and practices, and in a way that its consequences can be controlled.

Another important issue is the legal dimension of asylum in Turkey. The legal framework for combating regular and irregular migration needs to be effectively strengthened. Turkey's migration legislation under the Law on Foreigners and International Protection should be reviewed and reorganized in line with the needs. Following the dispersion of asylum-seekers in cities, they should be gathered in certain centers and living conditions in these areas should be improved. Where the war has ended, plans for the repatriation of asylum-seekers should be prepared quickly. In addition, in the framework of international cooperation, safe zones should be established in areas where the war has ended and refugees should be repatriated to their home countries.

In order to cope with the migrant problem, support from local governments is also required. This is because public services such as transportation, housing, environmental cleaning, police services and water supply in urban areas under the responsibility of municipalities are among

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the areas most affected by mass migration. In this context, the duties of local governments should be revised and local government representatives should be given a voice in the state's policy development process. In addition, within their areas of responsibility, local governments should be given authority over issues such as the admission, settlement and residence of migrants in the city. Efforts should be made to create social environmental awareness among migrants through local governments. Local governments should be allocated additional resources for the migrant population and necessary arrangements should be made to increase the number of personnel.

At the societal level, Turkish people need to be made aware of migrants and asylum seekers. In addition, events should be organized to raise public awareness. In this way, political awareness of the social, economic and environmental dimensions of the problem can also be raised among the world community. In addition to the Turkish public, asylum seekers also need to be made aware of this process; otherwise, their integration into Turkish society will not be ensured.

A realistic and comprehensive economic, political, social and cultural program should be developed for the integration of refugees into society. This program should prioritize important issues such as education, health and social peace. Effective public relations work should be carried out to counter the negative public opinion against asylum-seekers and the public should be informed. Social policies should be developed for the temporary adaptation of migrants to the society and this process should be accelerated. Special institutions can be established for the effective implementation of the temporary adaptation process. Turkish education and general education opportunities should be provided especially for children and young asylum seekers in order to ensure their adaptation to Turkey. Permanent solutions should be developed to ensure that asylum-seekers learn Turkish and realistic policies should be developed through scientific and academic studies in this field. For example, skilled and educated Syrians in Turkey should be utilized in areas of need, and individuals with vocational technical training and qualifications should be included in the labor market. The participation of the skilled refugee population in the productive population will contribute to the development of the country's economy. For this purpose, diploma equivalency issues should be resolved and these individuals should be prioritized among asylum seekers granted citizenship.

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Finally, in response to the risk of new migration, the state needs to increase border security and carry out stricter controls. Turkey should establish an asylum seeker policy based on stricter controls and all migrants should be registered and allowed to reside only in authorized areas. Otherwise, migrants residing without authorization should be deported. In addition, migrants should not be allowed to go to cities outside of shelters, and migrants in cities should be urgently gathered in shelters.

In Syria, Assad's departure and his replacement by the leader of Hayat Tahrir al-Sham (HTS) could complicate the process of repatriation of Syrian refugees in Turkey. Such a change would create significant uncertainties about Syria's future and security. However, several key steps can be taken for the return of Syrian refugees:

1. Stabilizing the Security Situation in Syria: Turkey can build an international coalition to stabilize the security situation in Syria for the return of Syrian refugees. Under the leadership of HTS, it is difficult to create a fully secure environment, especially in some areas in the north. However, it is possible to create a safe zone and provide incentives for refugees to return there. The role of the international community in this process will be critical.

2. International Cooperation and Coordination: Turkey can contribute to Syria's reconstruction process in cooperation with the United Nations (UN), the European Union (EU) and other regional powers. In this process, infrastructure projects and shelter facilities should be provided to facilitate the return of refugees. In addition, economic support should be provided to incentivize return and create opportunities for refugees to find jobs and sustain their lives upon their return.

3. Creating Safe Zones in Syria: Safe zones can be established in HTS-controlled areas. In these areas, infrastructure, education and health services can be provided for refugees. At the same time, social cohesion programs can be developed so that the local population in these areas can accept the refugees. Such zones could encourage the voluntary return of asylum seekers.

4. Investment and Reconstruction Support to Syria: To encourage the return of refugees, Turkey could invest in Syria to address infrastructure deficiencies. This investment should meet basic needs such as water supply, shelter, education and health services. In coordination with

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international actors, these infrastructure projects should be implemented and the return process should be made economically sustainable.

5. Supporting Social Integration of Asylum Seekers: Turkey should keep in mind that the return process needs to be managed not only in terms of physical but also social and cultural cohesion. The new government structure and social environment in Syria may affect the return of Syrians. Returnees will need social cohesion programs to ensure social peace. These programs may include psychological support, workforce training, and local government support for integration processes.

6. International Assistance to Internally Displaced Persons in Syria: Turkey should coordinate international assistance to ensure that other displaced Syrians are assisted following the return of asylum seekers. Together with the UN, the EU and other humanitarian organizations, projects could be launched to ensure the safe return of refugees and their participation in the reconstruction process in Syria.

7. Integration with the Reconstruction Process inside Syria: It is important that Syrians returning to Syria are involved in the reconstruction process in the country. This creates an opportunity for them to contribute to labor needs, infrastructure projects and development processes inside the country. The Turkish government could develop projects to integrate educated and skilled labor into the Syrian reconstruction process.

8. Regulating the Legal Status of Asylum Seekers: Turkey should make legal arrangements for asylum-seekers who wish to return to Syria and provide them with the necessary documents and legal protection during the return process. Legal and bureaucratic facilities should be provided for the resettlement process of returning Syrians.

9. Psychological and Social Support: Syrian asylum-seekers who have suffered tremendous trauma during the civil war in Syria should receive psychological support upon their return. Turkey can develop a psychological support program in cooperation with international aid organizations for Syrians to benefit from this support. This is an important step towards social peace.

10. Incentives for the Voluntary Return of Refugees: Turkey should encourage the voluntary return of Syrian refugees. In this framework, incentives such as financial support, job

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opportunities, housing support can be offered to returning asylum-seekers initially. However, the return of asylum-seekers should be voluntary and without any pressure. The changing political structure in Syria may make the return of Syrian refugees more complicated, but this process can be managed with international cooperation and comprehensive planning. In promoting the return of refugees, Turkey can actively use international assistance and regional cooperation to ensure security and enable Syrians to contribute to the reconstruction process.

General Evaluation

Turkey hosts the largest number of Syrian refugees in the world. It has also historically been one of the destination countries for migrant flows. Especially in recent years, the increase in the number of asylum-seekers and refugees from neighboring countries demonstrates Turkey's global importance in this field. Migrants from geographies such as the Middle East, Central Asia, Africa and West Asia largely prefer Turkey. Political instability and internal conflicts in countries such as the Middle East, Afghanistan and Syria have increased the number of people seeking refuge in Turkey, some of whom use Turkey as a transit country while others aim to continue their lives here. The situation of Syrian asylum seekers differs from other migrant groups.

Turkey's refugee problem is not only a humanitarian crisis, but has become a multidimensional social, economic and political issue and occupies an important place on the country's agenda. The solution to this problem will directly affect Turkey's social structure, domestic political balances and international image in the long run. In the future, policies towards asylum-seekers will be one of the key factors determining both domestic political balances and Turkey's role at the global level.

Migration movements, especially from the Middle East, have become a multidimensional issue that requires national and international cooperation and coordination. This situation deeply affects the economic, socio-cultural and demographic structures, public order and security of countries. The migration crisis can only be managed through mutual dialogue and international cooperation. For example, despite the requirement to protect the right to life enshrined in Article 1 of the European Convention on Human Rights, European Union (EU) countries avoid taking responsibility for protecting the lives of people at risk of losing their lives due to war. The EU's approach to solving the refugee and asylum seeker problem elsewhere does not offer a concrete

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and sustainable solution. The rate of resettlement of Syrian migrants in European countries is very low, and Europe, with a population of 500 million, has accepted only 1 million Syrian migrants. This situation reveals the lack of a solution-oriented approach.

If well managed, migration flows bring economic benefits, new ideas and skills to countries of settlement. However, poorly managed migration movements can lead to unregistered labor, social tensions and human rights violations. Problems with Syrian asylum-seekers in Turkey can lead to various negative consequences, particularly in terms of public order and security. In this context, migrants from countries such as Syria may cause a loss of qualified labor force in their countries of origin, while causing imbalances in the labor market in Turkey.

Today, the situation of migrants and asylum seekers is managed in line with the 1951 Geneva Convention. However, this convention cannot meet today's migration conditions with the old conditions. The increasing burden of migration worldwide has become a major burden not only for specific countries but for the entire international community. In this context, the need for an international convention that will provide lasting and sustainable solutions and effective migration management is increasing day by day.

Looking at the situation in Turkey, a significant number of migrants do not stay in shelters and settle in cities. This shows the efforts of asylum-seekers to create individual opportunities for themselves. However, the fact that they do not speak Turkish, are unskilled and work unregistered in metropolitan cities causes asylum-seekers to face significant social and economic problems. This situation causes them to be employed in low-paid jobs especially in metropolitan cities and increases social disharmony.

Despite the financial resources Turkey has spent so far, Syrian refugees face serious problems. Children, youth and adults cannot receive education, cannot access health services and live under poor living conditions due to economic difficulties. Problems such as lack of social communication due to lack of language skills, domestic violence and social disharmony negatively affect the quality of life of asylum-seekers. Turkish citizens also face various problems due to Syrian asylum-seekers, especially in times of economic crisis. The spending of economic resources on asylum-seekers is criticized by some segments of the society and this situation reinforces the view that asylum-seekers impose a great economic burden on the country.

The Change of Government in Syria and its Impact on Refugees in Turkey

A change of government in Syria could have a direct impact on the process of resolving the refugee crisis in the country. The replacement of the Assad regime by the current leadership of Hayat Tahrir al-Sham (Hayat Tahrir al-Sham) could be an important step towards ending the civil war in Syria. However, this change would entail not only an administrative transformation, but also the need to rebuild the country after the war and ensure national unity and stability. Turkey has an important role to play in the return of Syrian refugees. Participation in Syria's reconstruction process and steps such as the creation of a safe zone can ensure Turkey's involvement in this process. However, this process will be possible not only through a political solution, but also through humanitarian aid, infrastructure support and international cooperation.

After the change of administration, Turkey will need to reshape its refugee policy. With the establishment of safe zones in Syria and the end of the civil war in Syria, Turkey needs to support the return of refugees and provide international support for the reconstruction of settlements. This process should also be carried out in coordination with the international community and the process of return to safe zones should be managed properly. Turkey can develop the necessary policies to accelerate the return of refugees and should with international organizations to ensure a fair, sustainable and safe return process.

In conclusion, in order to solve the refugee problem, Turkey needs to improve not only its domestic politics but also its regional and global cooperation. While the change of administration in Syria offers an important opportunity in this process, it can be predicted that Turkey will be more effective in solving this problem with international cooperation and strategic planning.

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